

ARMOR

Fighting Antimicrobial Resistance in Livestock Farming

Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) is a rising threat to public health, food safety, livelihoods, and sustainable development of the agricultural sector.

Microbes can evolve and share adaptations to withstand antimicrobial treatments. It is essential that we reduce our antimicrobial use to slow the development of resistant bacterial strains and maintain the effectiveness of live-saving treatments.

Hence, there is an urgent need for innovative solutions in farming to protect animal health and welfare whilst achieving further reductions in veterinary antimicrobial use.

The ARMOR Cluster is providing solutions to support the agricultural sector in preventing and counteracting AMR:

- Information materials, recommendations, and guidelines for farmers for the development of animal health & welfare plans
- Identification of levers, incentives, indicators, and socio-technical solutions to support antimicrobial use (AMU) reduction at farm level
- Cost-benefit analyses of reduced antimicrobial usage
- Feed additives and alternative feeding strategies to increase the resilience of farm animals
- Alternatives to antimicrobials for the management of bacterial infections in animals

Discover our solutions to wear an AMR-proof ARMoR

ARMoR

Scan the QR codes or click on the logos to find out more

AMRILS

AVANT

This factsheet has been produced by ICONS in the context of the Horizon Results Boosterservices delivered to DISARM (GA N. 817591), ROADMAP (GA N. 817626), AVANT (GA N. 862829), HealthyLivestock (GA N. 773436) and AMR in livestock systems. This product does not reflect the views of the European Commission.

